

Research paper

Flood risk assessment of cultural heritage sites near lakes via advanced hydrodynamic modeling and digital technologies

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ABSTRACT

Cultural heritage flood risk assessments demand high-resolution, physics-based modeling frameworks capable of capturing complex terrain in diverse hydrological environments, and the subtle dynamics that threaten the relics. This study develops and applies such a framework at the lakeside archaeological site of Smuszewo, Poland, where flood hazards could arise from a combination of overland runoff and dynamic lake-stage fluctuations. To this end, we applied a high-resolution modeling approach combining overland terrain obtained via LiDAR and drone photogrammetry, and a digitized lake bathymetric model, within a HEC-RAS 2D Rain-on-Grid framework that enables detailed simulation of runoff–lake interactions and site-specific flood scenarios across design storms. We evaluate three scenarios: (i) model calibration using a five-day rainfall-stage event, (ii) the hydraulic impact of including versus omitting explicit lake bathymetry, across five design storms (1–50-year return periods); and (iii) a margin-to-failure analysis simulating lake-level rise from 0.00 to +1.50 m. Results show that omitting bathymetry underestimates peak flows for frequent storms due to artificial ponding on flat, dry-initiated surfaces (vs. realistic depths and wet cells enabling accurate volume propagation), whereas impact diminishes for the higher return periods. However, even under the worst-case scenario, an extreme storm on top of a +1.5 m lake-stage rise, more than 1 m of freeboard remains. Our findings demonstrate the critical role of multiscale, high-resolution terrain and physics-driven methods—and lay the groundwork for future digital-twin implementations, predictive maintenance strategies, and cloud-based simulations in cultural heritage flood-risk management.

Secondary keywords

Lake Bathymetry; Hydrodynamic Modeling

1. Introduction

Flooding, identified as a costly natural peril globally [1], is not dominated by fluvial extremes alone; closed-basin and regulated lakes supply the hydraulic head that controls floodplain inundation [2]. Europe has not been spared: in 2024 the Copernicus European State of the Climate report registered the extensive inundation since 2013, with

river discharges above the high-flow threshold along 30 % of the monitored network [3], while routed reconstructions of the last seven decades revealed an 11 % expansion in event footprints [4]. Trends of similar complexity demand flood-risk methodologies capable of resolving both overland runoff and dynamic stage fluctuations within lake basins. Lake-heritage interactions present a particularly underexplored dimension of this challenge.

Scholarly attention to cultural heritage (CH) under hydro-climatic stress has evolved from a nascent thematic niche in 2003 to a multi-disciplinary corpus spanning architecture, geoarchaeology, climatology, and disaster governance by the mid-2010s [5]. UNESCO's early warning

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that water is “Europe’s most pervasive weathering agent” [6] presaged an era in which gradual forcings such as sea-level rise, permafrost decay, or desertification compound the frequency of acute floods [7].

Empirical studies verify such mechanisms: shifting hydrothermal regimes intensify winter decay of wooden ecclesiastical ensembles in southeastern Poland [8], and promote salt crystallization, corrosion, and structural fatigue in masonry [7]. Building on these insights, recent studies propose management frameworks [9], hazard mapping techniques [10], and loss quantification methods [11]. Yet, the lack of harmonized cross-national datasets [12] constrains quantitative indices [13,14]. The deficit is emphasized by ex-post analyses of 2022 floods in central Italy, which revealed systematic exposure misclassification for 14 damaged assets [15]. Despite this progress, existing CH flood-risk studies focus predominantly on riverine [16] or coastal hazards [17]. CH assets situated within or adjacent to closed lake basins, where both pluvial inputs and antecedent water levels govern inundation dynamics, remain largely unaddressed in the literature.

The Late Bronze/Early Iron Age fortified settlement at Smuszewo, Poland, perched on an isthmus between two post-glacial lakes (Fig. 1), survives today because anaerobic lacustrine sediments inhibited decay. Yet this hydrological buffer is destabilized by both anthropogenic drainage and climatic perturbations. Hundreds of Polish and Central European heritage sites lie in similar environments—once waterlogged landscapes now at risk from climate change and human intervention—making Smuszewo an instructive case for assessing mid-19th-century to present-day impacts and for modeling processes that affect still-preserved relics. The need to expand arable land (including meadows and pastures) encouraged farmers in the 19th and 20th centuries to drain the valley, which lowered the lake levels, exposing the wood and subjecting it to aerobic decomposition. Conversely, convective downpours drive ephemeral surges that raise the water level, while fertilizer-laden runoff from neighboring arable fields fuels eutrophication and biochemical attack.

Recurrent stage oscillations thus may execute a dual attritional mechanism: mechanical fatigue of exposed wood and chemical alteration of buried assemblages.

The archaeological oak structures preserved within the Smuszewo basin face deterioration when exposed to fluctuating moisture regimes. To understand this vulnerability, long-term observations [18] demonstrate that even temporarily drained waterlogged oak can suffer rapid biochemical decay and microbial colonization. The study documents that transition from anaerobic to aerobic conditions triggers oxidative

degradation, loss of cellulose, and accelerated microbial attack, leading to structural disintegration of wooden relics [18]. Björdal [19] further identifies soft rot fungi as key decomposers capable of thriving even at low oxygen concentrations, particularly under dynamic water tables where transient aeration allows colonization without complete drying.

This implies that in the context of Smuszewo, stage oscillations of even ± 0.25 m may not overtly inundate or expose the entire site, but still intermittently disturb the redox and microbial equilibrium. Wood that was once stabilized by permanent submersion may become vulnerable not from catastrophic flood but from a slow oscillatory regime that allows fungal establishment. Such conditions can be damaging for oak, whose apparent external preservation may mask internal structural weakening due to lignin-targeting degradation, as observed in multiple European lake-dwelling sites [19]. Effective conservation must therefore account not only for overt flood or drought risk, but also for seasonal or sub-seasonal exposure cycles that subtly breach the anaerobic preservation envelope. Hence, modeling must reproduce both short-term pluvial inputs and antecedent lake geometry to capture redox swings.

To meet the dual requirements, we employ the Hydrologic Engineering Center’s River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) through its two-dimensional Rain-on-Grid (RoG) solver, which imposes precipitation directly on computational cells and solves hydrologic and hydraulic equations in a unified framework [20–22]. RoG is adept at routing flow across complex micro-topographies and infrastructure [23]; yet its fidelity is highly sensitive to digital elevation model (DEM) resolution, with peak-stage attenuation and hydrograph flattening becoming conspicuous as grid spacing coarsens from 1 m to 5 m [24–26]. Recent benchmarking against TELEMAC-2D corroborates the method’s strengths—and highlights parameter sensitivities—when simulating short-duration mountain floods [27]. No study has yet examined in a structured way how the way lakes are modeled in RoG frameworks, especially whether bathymetry and initial water levels are included, affects predicted water stages for CH sites near lakes. The gap matters because lakes behave very differently from rivers: their large storage capacity slows changes in water level, but if their depth or initial water level is not set correctly, model results can yield misleading estimates of flooding potential.

To address this gap, the present study delivers the first systematic evaluation of lake representation in a RoG framework for CH flood risk. It couples empirical calibration with scenario-based sensitivity analysis. First, we calibrate a high-resolution RoG model for the Czeszewo Lake

Fig. 1. The Czeszewo Lake and its vicinity as located in Poland (A) and the setting of archaeological site between two lakes on the lower part of postglacial valley (B - oblique aerial photographs, 5.07.2014).

basin using a five-day event constrained by South-station rainfall and continuous lake-stage observations. Second, we examine lake representation by contrasting two configurations: a bathymetry-integrated DEM with stage-defined wet cells, and Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) derived bare-earth DEM initiated dry except for measured water surfaces. Third, we investigate the potential for overtopping by deriving the lake-stage increment at which freeboard is exhausted. Section 2 details the geomorphic, hydro-meteorological, and land-cover datasets, including drone-based DEM acquisition and hietograph synthesis. Section 3 outlines mesh construction, infiltration parameterization, calibration metrics, and the staged sensitivity workflow. Section 4 presents calibration performance, lake-scheme contrasts, and overtopping thresholds; Section 5 interprets uncertainties, methodological novelty, and generalizability to lake-fringed heritage sites. Concluding remarks distil actionable guidance for heritage flood-risk assessments and propose research extensions toward longer-term morphodynamic coupling.

The ensuing analysis therefore delivers the first systematic evaluation of lake representation in a RoG framework for CH risk, coupling empirical calibration with scenario-based sensitivity to inform both engineering practice and conservation policy.

2. Study area and data

2.1. Site description

The study site is a partly waterlogged fortified settlement dated to the Late Bronze Age/Early Iron Age. It was first exposed in 1863 during land-reclamation at the base of a post-glacial valley and the lake's western shore. Lowered water levels revealed wooden breakwater structures in the peat–mineral valley fill [28,29].

Excavations from 1959 to 1966 uncovered remnants of wooden buildings and the base of a timber–earth rampart, analogous to larger finds at Biskupin (~25 km South-East; [30,31]). A 2004 geophysical survey mapped the settlement's regular plan and detected charcoal from burned rampart sections [32] (Fig. 2). Aerial reconnaissance produced no new features, reflecting the subtle nature of the buried remains (Fig. 1B).

Based on analysis of ceramics and metal artifacts, archaeologists

initially dated the site to 500–400 BCE [33], but dendrochronology of four oak samples from the breakwaters indicates a mid-8th century BCE construction [34]. Wooden remains lie beneath ~1 m of sediment in the settlement's interior, with preservation controlled by moisture and anaerobic conditions [18]. Digital Terrain Model (DTM) analysis on the western side shows a missing rampart section, likely eroded by higher lake waves before reclamation.

2.2. Rainfall and stage data

The research used data on precipitation recorded at three nearby meteorological stations of the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - National Research Institute (IMGW-PIB): Gołańcz (hereinafter referred to as Gołańcz), Chrzastowo (Chrast) and Janowiec Wielkopolski (Janwlkp). In Poland, precipitation measurements are conducted using the standard IMGW-PIB measurement and observation network. Rainfall measurement data are directly available in databases on the <https://hydro.imgw.pl/#/list/meteo> and <https://danepubliczne.imgw.plwebsites> and on the MONITOR IMGW-PIB platform as operational data. For the sake of both clarity and brevity, we demonstrate the comparison of daily rainfall records for the years 2013, 2016, and 2018 (Fig. 3).

For the purposes of the work, daily precipitation data from the period 1954–2024 were used for the Gołańcz station, 10-minute precipitation data for 2008–2024 for the Janwlkp station, and 10-minute precipitation and direction and additionally speed of wind more than 5, 10, 15 and 20 m/s for the Chrast station from the years 2012–2024. These stations were considered crucial for conducting a hydrological analysis and assessing the potential impact of precipitation on the archaeological site in Smuszewo. They provide precipitation data and others meteorological data with different temporal and spatial ranges, enabling a comprehensive assessment of local and regional climatic conditions. The stations were selected due to their location in relation to the Smuszewo settlement. Gołańcz is located northwest of Smuszewo (approx. 9 km), hence it was considered a reference meteorological station, important for local analyses. It serves as the main source of base data. The Janowiec Wielkopolski station is located approx. 16 km to the south, while the furthest from it, to the north, is Chrzastowo (approx. 32 km). Both

Fig. 2. Simplified plan of the settlement and preserved relics based on the interpretation of geophysical survey data [32]. Legend: 1 – long wooden houses divided into smaller ‘compartments’ (c. 6.5/7 × 7/7.5 m each) in which circular, stone hearths (2) were; 3 – main wooden paved street; 4 – side wooden streets; 5 – scatter of the burnt upper part of the rampart; 6 – breakwaters (?); 7 – gate (?); 8 – excavated area as visible at the HEXAGON image (16.02.1975).

Fig. 3. Daily precipitation hyetographs for Janwłkp, Chrzast, and Golańcz stations in 2013, 2016, and 2018.

stations can be a source of verification data, useful for validating regional data. The layout of stations around Smuszewo – north-west (Golańcz), north (Chrzastowo), south (Janowiec Włkp.) can enable the identification of local weather anomalies. The preliminary analysis allows us to assume that the precipitation data in the two stations Golańcz and Janowiec Włkp. are well correlated spatially. On the other hand, the Chrzastowo station shows differences, which is probably related to its considerable distance from Smuszewo and local anomalies in the environmentally specific Noteć river valley, in the range of which the station is located.

Janwłkp and Golańcz correlate strongly and consistently ($r \approx 0.84-0.86$). By contrast, Chrzast (northeast) shows volatile correlations with both stations (Janwłkp-Chrzast: $0.43 \rightarrow 0.88 \rightarrow 0.58$; Chrzast-Golańcz: $0.44 \rightarrow 0.82 \rightarrow 0.69$). Consequently, Janwłkp serves as the sub-daily rainfall proxy; Chrzast was excluded from calibration.

The research also used data on the water surface elevation in Czeszewo Lake (Fig. 4–5), derived from direct field measurements. The lake is not covered by systematic water level measurements within the IMGW-PIB network. Local hydrological monitoring of water levels in Czeszewo Lake has been carried out since May 2024 as part of the TRIQUETRA project [35]. Regular measurements consist of automatic recording of water level changes in a continuous course using a

ventilated water level recorder DL/N64 (STS, Switzerland), providing measurement of water column pressure with full compensation of atmospheric pressure thanks to the built-in capillary. The recorder is located in the eastern part of the lake basin (Fig. 4). The condition for correct recording of parameters was the appropriate installation of the device, ensuring a constant level of attachment of the above-water part of the recorder. This was achieved by installing the recorder in a casing pipe driven into the bottom of the water reservoir (difficult to access, reed zone).

The device used allows for recording the pressure of the water column with an accuracy of 0.1 % (in practice, less than 3 mm). To control the stability of the assembly and the compliance of the obtained results with the actual water level, an underground control benchmark was installed at the lake shore, which is leveled to the national geodetic network of detailed elevation networks in the Amsterdam reference system using an optical level. The verification of the reference level of the benchmark was performed on the state benchmark of the detailed height control no. 61,881,625,035. H catalog benchmark is 99.86 m (Smuszewo, building no. 18, northern wall), H average of five Real Time Kinematics (RTK) measurements = 99.87 m (PLEVRF2007-NH system - "Amsterdam").

The recorded data is read in the field by connecting the dataloggers

Fig. 4. Location of Water Surface Elevation (WSE) gauge and lake outlet.

Fig. 5. Water surface elevation of Czeszewo Lake from May to December 2024, showing a gradual decline through late autumn followed by a rise in December.

to a laptop and transferring the results.

Lake stage starts at 88.41 m and declines quasi-linearly over the summer dry spell to 88.06 m on 2 November, therefore a 0.35 m drop in 165 days (Fig. 5). A late-autumn precipitation surge then raises stage by ≈ 0.21 m, which ends the year at 88.27 m.

To assess long-term rainfall behavior, we analyzed extreme-precipitation indices at the Gotańcz gauge over 1956–2024. The precipitation

time series analysis reveals characteristic patterns of temporal stationarity across multiple extreme precipitation indices. The distributional characteristics and temporal trends for all precipitation metrics are summarized in Table 1. Fig. 6 demonstrates the annual 95th-percentile daily totals, which evince an ordinary least squares slope of $+0.011$ mm yr^{-1} ($p = 0.463$), flanked by pronounced inter-annual volatility with a coefficient of variation of 21.9 % (Table 1). The temporal structure

Table 1
Summary statistics and distributional parameters for annual precipitation extremes at Golańcz station (1956–2024).

Metric	Mean	Range	CV (%)	Skewness	Kurtosis (excess)	Dispersion Ratio (Variance/Mean)	Trend (mm/yr or d/yr)	p-value
95th percentile (mm)	11.4	12.2	21.9	—	—	—	+0.011	0.463
Annual maximum (mm)	—	82.3	—	1.524	3.076	—	-0.088	0.320
Heavy days (≥ 20 mm)	2.4	6	—	—	—	0.993	+0.003	0.734

Fig. 6. Annual 95th percentile daily precipitation at Golańcz station (1956–2024).

exhibits a range of 12.2 mm, spanning from 5.1 to 17.1 mm over the 69-year observational epoch.

Fig. 7 shows a trend of $-0.088 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$ ($p = 0.320$), skewness $\gamma = 1.524$, and excess kurtosis $\kappa = 3.076$. The 82.3 mm range reflects extreme convective events in 1977 and 2016.

Fig. 8 demonstrates effectively trend-less behavior ($+0.003 \text{ d yr}^{-1}$, $p = 0.734$). The temporal distribution exhibits a mean frequency of 2.4 events per year with a dispersion ratio (variance/mean) of 0.993, approximating unity and confirming consistency with Poisson-distributed occurrences. The discrete range spans 0 to 6 events annually, with apparent clustering during specific decadal periods.

Collectively, the station record is consistent with the null hypothesis of stationarity, in agreement with Pińskwar et al. [36].

2.3. Synthetic hyetographs

Synthetic Hyetographs of 10 min temporal resolution were constructed based on local Intensity-Duration-Frequency (IDF) curves for the Smuszewo location ($52^{\circ}53'34.48''\text{N}/ 17^{\circ}23'33.74''\text{E}$) (Fig. 9) using the Alternating Blocks method [37] for 50-, 10-, 5-, 2- and 1-year return periods (Fig. 10). The work uses data from the Polish Atlas of Rain Intensity PANDa (<https://atlaspanda.pl>) regarding the intensity of reliable rainfall with a specified duration and exceedance probability $p= 2\%$ and 10% (data acquisition certificate 0325/1099,929/3), 20% and 50% (data acquisition certificate 0325/2795,467/3) and 99% and 100% (data acquisition certificate 0325/7953,534/3). The range of rainfall durations was $t= 5\text{--}4320$ min. The calculations used the average rainfall intensity $\text{dm}^3/(\text{s}\cdot\text{ha})$ within the provided confidence intervals.

Fig. 7. Annual maximum daily precipitation at Golańcz station (1956–2024).

Fig. 8. Annual count of heavy precipitation days (≥ 20 mm) at Golańcz station (1956–2024).

Fig. 9. IDF curves for Smuszewo ($52^{\circ}53'34.48''N$, $17^{\circ}23'33.74''E$) showing rainfall intensity ($dm^3/(s \cdot ha)$) versus event duration (5–4 320 min) at exceedance probabilities of 2 %, 10 %, 20 %, 50 %, 99 % and 100 %.

Atlas (PANDa) is an online platform containing information on reliable rainfall intensities for all cities in Poland. The atlas in digital format contains a catalog of nearly 13,000 local precipitation models developed for each mesh (with a resolution of 5 km) of the regular grid dividing the area of Poland [38].

2.4. Terrain and bathymetry

We downloaded 1 m DTM and Digital Surface Model (DSM) tiles (ASC, EPSG:2180) from Poland’s Geoportal using QGIS’s Data Downloader, covering the Czeszewo Lake and its catchment. Source data are 2014 airborne LiDAR [39,40]. Tiles were reprojected to UTM 33 N GeoTIFF and median-filtered (11×11) to remove interpolation artifacts.

As part of the task to obtain a highly accurate DTM and DSM, a photogrammetric mission was carried out using the Yuneec H520 RTK drone equipped with a 20-megapixel E90X camera. Flights were

conducted at an altitude of 120 m above ground level, which allowed for a ground sampling distance of approximately 3.5 cm. The mission was planned in a grid flight pattern, using an 85 % forward overlap and 75 % side overlap between images. Data acquisition was performed under favorable conditions with clear skies, no wind, and stable lighting, in order to minimize shadows and image distortions. The drone’s positioning relied on the RTK system, with real-time corrections delivered via a cellular network. By doing so, we achieved centimeter-level geolocation accuracy without the need for ground control points.

The collected images were processed using photogrammetric software Pix4Dmapper. The workflow included importing the images, aligning them, generating a dense point cloud, and creating the DSM. To derive the DTM, the point cloud was filtered to remove surface elements such as vegetation. A high-resolution orthophoto was also generated based on the processed data.

The final DTM and DSM models underwent accuracy assessment. Position verification was based on RTK data, and the resulting root mean

Fig. 10. Synthetic hyetographs of 10 min temporal resolution constructed using the Alternating Blocks method for 50-, 10-, 5-, 2- and 1-year return periods for a 12 h event.

square errors (RMS) ranged between 2–3 cm in both horizontal and vertical dimensions, confirming the high quality and precision of the deliverables. The data were exported in GeoTIFF and LAS formats, which allowed further processing in a Geographic Information System (GIS) environment.

Originally developed by the Inland Fisheries Institute (IRŚ) (Fig. 11),

First, the scanned bathymetric plan (Fig. 11a) was georeferenced using distinctive landscape features such as the shoreline and the mouths of inflowing streams. Next, the isobaths were digitized and overlaid on a contemporary orthophoto map, allowing for spatial verification of their accuracy (Fig. 11b). A raster bathymetric model of the lakebed was generated through morphology interpolation techniques (Fig. 11c).

Fig. 11. Conversion of the analog bathymetric plan by the IRŚ into digital format: a) georeferenced scan of the bathymetric plan based on distinctive features, b) digitized isobaths overlaid on a contemporary orthophoto map, c) lakebed model of Czeszewo Lake obtained through interpolation and profile lines, d) depth profile.

Additionally, a depth profile was created to illustrate the variation in lake depth along a selected transect (Fig. 11d).

The DTM and DSM were integrated with a historical bathymetric map from 1961 [41]. The final continuous elevation model is created by merging the bathymetric data with the DTM/DSM using a custom script that harmonized raster resolution and spatial extent. The isobaths were vectorized and assigned elevation values relative to the lake's mean water level (88.2 m a.s.l.) in the Polish vertical reference system KRON86. A continuous raster bathymetric model was then generated using surface-fitting techniques based on the contour lines, by applying morphological functions at a resolution consistent with the elevation model (Fig. 12). The original vertical and planimetric accuracy of source lidar data is estimated at 0.15 m.

3. Methodology

This study employed a multi-tiered approach to systematically assess flood vulnerability at lakeside CH sites, with the overall methodological workflow illustrated in Fig. 13.

3.1. Rain-On-Grid model setup

3.1.1. Hydrodynamic solver and stability

The Hydrologic Engineering Center's River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) has matured into the hydraulics community's open-source workhorse, courtesy of the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' steady iteration and transparent numerical kernels [42]. Its most consequential and somewhat recent upgrade is the two-dimensional RoG capability, by which observed or remotely sensed precipitation is applied directly to computational cells, thereby collapsing the traditional hydrologic-hydraulic partition and permitting runoff generation, flow routing, and flood-wave propagation to be resolved within a single engine [20,21].

Within the 2D module, users may invoke either the parabolic Diffusion Wave scheme or one of two manifestations of the depth-averaged Shallow Water Equations (SWE): the hybrid Eulerian-Lagrangian formulation (SWE-ELM) and the fully Eulerian finite-difference solver (SWE-EM). The latter tackles the conservative form of the SWE—valid where horizontal length scales dwarf the flow depth—through an upwind discretisation that tracks the temporal evolution of water depth, h , and the depth-averaged velocity vector, V :

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla(Vh) = q \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (V\nabla)V = -g\nabla(h+z) + \nu_t \nabla^2 V - c_f V \quad (2)$$

where q represents source-sink terms such as rainfall and infiltration, g

is gravitational acceleration, z is bed elevation, ν_t is the horizontal eddy-viscosity coefficient, and c_f embodies bed-friction losses. Neglecting the advective and viscous terms simplifies (2) to the classic diffusion-wave momentum balance,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + g\nabla(h+z) = gS_f \quad (3)$$

which is computationally cheaper but less faithful when supercritical flows or rapid transients are present.

All schemes are executed over a structured mesh with boundary conditions prescribed along basin limits. To forestall numerical oscillations, the user-selected time step, Δt , must satisfy the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) criterion,

$$Cr = \frac{u\Delta t}{\Delta s} \quad (4)$$

where u is the characteristic wave speed and Δs the representative cell dimension. Although SWE-EM is an explicit solution scheme that requires Courant numbers to remain at or below unity for stability [43], practitioners generally iterate toward 1—which adapts both grid resolution and time step to local topographic gradients and flow regimes—to secure a stable, non-diffusive solution.

3.1.2. Basin area

The basin area of Czeszewo Lake was delineated through manual vectorization of basin boundaries based on publicly available data provided via a Web Map Service. The MPHP10k dataset defines the boundaries of administrative units used in Polish water management, including river basin districts (Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie), and is distributed under the CC BY 4.0 license, which permits data processing.

The MPHP10k data were loaded into a GIS environment using the WMS service available at: <https://mapy.isok.gov.pl/wms>. Based on the "Basic Basins" layer, the boundary of the Czeszewo Lake basin was manually vectorized for topological accuracy using QGIS editing tools. The delineated boundary was validated against reference layers, including a DTM and the hydrographic network. Where necessary, adjustments were made to the boundary, particularly in areas with complex terrain morphology.

The final basin boundary was exported to the shapefile format and reprojected to the UTM Zone 33 N coordinate system (EPSG:32,633), from the original PUWG 1992 system (EPSG:2180), in accordance with national GIS standards.

3.1.3. Mesh and boundary conditions

We used an unstructured 10×10 m mesh to balance computational speed with sufficient resolution of flow dynamics and water-surface

Fig. 12. DTM (left) and DSM (right) integrated with the bathymetry of Czeszewo Lake; basin area is presented with red solid line.

Comprehensive analysis of flood risk at cultural heritage lakeside sites

Fig. 13. Integrated framework for flood risk assessment at cultural heritage lakeside sites, employing RoG hydrodynamic modeling with experimental bathymetry configurations and multiple data acquisition techniques to evaluate flow dynamics, storage capacity, and subsurface risks through calibrated simulations.

gradients. Although this grid is coarser than the DEM, HEC-RAS’s subgrid processing preserves topographic detail by embedding elevation–volume and hydraulic properties from the high-resolution terrain [44]. For this basin (0.2–0.8 % slopes), we set a 5 min base time step, and keep the Courant number near unity under subcritical flows. A dynamic controller halves the time step—up to five times—down to ~10 s when stability criteria are breached, to ensure numerical stability during rapid wetting transitions.

3.1.4. Hydraulic resistance & infiltration parameterization

Within RoG, we applied the United States Department of Agriculture [45] (1986) Curve-Number (CN) excess-abstraction method for infiltration. The land cover was mapped with two 10 m rasters from ESA WorldCover 2020 [46]: one layer provides Manning’s n for momentum equations, the other supplies CNs (Antecedent Moisture Condition II) to the excess-abstraction routine [47]. Manning coefficients were taken as first-guess priors drawn from Cea et al., [48], and refined via the calibration in Section 3.2 (Final values in Table 2). The initial abstraction I_a was computed using the ratio $I_a = 0.1S$, where S is the potential maximum retention derived from CN. Whilst in theory the default ratio is $I_a = 0.2S$, studies show that significantly lower values are more realistic [49]. Therefore, an abstraction ratio of 0.1 represents a more applicable yet conservative approach. CN values are selected to reflect Antecedent Moisture Conditions II, which represents the standard

Table 2

Land-cover classes with assigned Manning roughness and USDA CNs used in the RoG model.

WorldCover class	ID	Manning n	CN
Cropland	40	0.050	78
Grassland	30	0.035	71
Tree cover	10	0.070	71
Bare vegetation	60	0.030	86
Herbaceous wetland	90	0.040	85
Built-up surfaces	50	0.100	84
Permanent water	80	0.025	100
No-data / outside basin	—	masked	-

average moisture condition used in conventional Soil Conservation Service (SCS)-CN applications.

3.2. Model calibration and validation (Block A)

The configuration employing the harmonized bathymetry within the elevation model, from now on called the bathymetry configuration, was calibrated over 10–14 July 2024. The period combines (i) a five-day storm sufficient to elicit a measurable stage response and (ii) the only continuous lake-stage record available (Fig. 14). We forced the model with 10-minute rainfall from the Janwlp pluviograph (total ≈ 46 mm; Fig. 14a) which exhibited the strongest correlation with Gołańcz daily totals (Pearson $r = 0.84$ (2013), 0.86 (2016) and 0.85 (2018)) compared to Chrzast (Pearson $r = 0.43$ (2013), 0.88 (2016) and 0.58 (2018)), as seen in Fig. 3.

Despite the moderate rainfall, lake-stage fluctuated by less than 0.10 m, indicating high storage capacity and flood attenuation within the lake basin. In the absence of reliable outlet discharge measurements, which would more directly integrate flow dynamics [50], we used stage as the primary calibration target, following precedent for small closed basins [51]. The configuration not using the bathymetry harmonization, from now on referred to as bare configuration, is introduced in Section 3.3.1.

3.3. Experiment matrix

Building on calibration, we now test sensitivities using synthetic storms to quantify bathymetry and stage effects on flood metrics. Design storms, standardized rainfall events defined by duration, return period, and intensity, are useful in hydrological modeling, as they drive predicted runoff and peak discharges in flood scenarios [52]. The calibrated model was driven through two blocks of synthetic design storms in order to (i) isolate the hydraulic impact of lake-bed representation and (ii) determine the stage rise that extinguishes freeboard at the monument’s sill. All simulations adopt the five intensity–duration hyetographs derived from the site-specific IDF curves (return periods 1, 2, 5, 10, 50 years).

Fig. 14. (a) Ten-minute rainfall hyetograph for the calibration event (10–14 July 2024; total depth \approx 46 mm); (b) Daily lake-stage record.

3.3.1. Lake-representation experiments (Block B)

Including bathymetric detail in hydrodynamic models is key to computational fidelity [53]. This is especially true in lakes, where complex topography strongly affects flow and inundation [54]. Comparing bathymetry-informed and bathymetry-deficient models quantifies how subsurface topography alters hydrodynamic responses.

Contemporary investigations have demonstrated that the accuracy of bathymetric representation significantly impacts the spatial structure of hydrodynamic processes [55], with complex geometry and topography fundamentally altering circulation patterns and water quality dynamics [56]. We run two simulations, one with explicit bathymetry, and one with simplified topography, to isolate bathymetric effects.

This lets us quantify bathymetry's effect on peak discharge, inundation extents and depths, velocity fields, and flood-wave timing. In Block B the simulation is executed twice per return period. The bathymetry variant uses the drone DEM with isobaths and sets initial water level to the mean July stage; the bare variant uses the raw ALS DEM with all cells at that stage, mimicking a constant lake level. Comparison of the paired runs quantifies the degree to which explicit bathymetry alters peak discharge, inundation depth, and velocity fields.

3.3.2. Stage-increment sensitivity (Block C)

Multi-model ensembles agree on a moderate wetting trend for central-western Poland. Bias-corrected EURO-CORDEX RCMs (0.11°) indicate an ensemble-median increase of 3–5 % in annual precipitation totals by 2030 (RCP 4.5) and 10–15 % by 2050 (RCP 8.5) [57]. CMIP-6 GCM downscaling centered on Wielkopolska corroborates these tendencies, projecting a +2–7.5 % augmentation in mean annual totals and an upward shift in the > 20 mm and > 30 mm classes throughout 2026–2100 [58]. A dedicated hazard-mapping exercise for the Wielkopolska voivodeship anticipates 20–30 % more days ≥ 20 mm in 2021–2050 and up to 40–80 % more by 2071–2100, with the frequency of ≥ 50 mm days potentially doubling under SSP5–8.5 [59].

The IPCC AR6 assigns high confidence to increased extreme precipitation and pluvial flooding across Europe—except the Mediterranean—under $>1.5^\circ\text{C}$ warming, a judgement partially echoed by other studies, which foresee contrasting trends within the Mediterranean itself: increases in the north (e.g., Italy, Balkans) but declining magnitudes in the south (e.g., Maghreb), albeit with paradoxical intensification of rare, high-impact extremes even in drying regions [60]. Thermodynamic first principles reinforce these numerical

projections: saturation-specific humidity rises at $\approx 7\% \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Clausius–Clapeyron scaling), a rate that observational syntheses confirm for hourly and sub-daily extremes across mid-latitudes [61,62].

Empirical limnological evidence already registers a climatically consistent response. A 25-lake survey extending from 1963 to 2022 documents statistically significant rises of $+3.5 \text{ cm decade}^{-1}$ in mean stages and $+4.6 \text{ cm decade}^{-1}$ in minima, while maxima remain largely unchanged [63]. Linear extrapolation of these rates to mid-century implies a baseline increment of 0.15–0.25 m in the absence of any enhancement of event rainfall. When superposed upon the ensemble-median precipitation uplift ($\approx 10\%$), and recognizing the non-linear translation of rainfall to runoff in small, low-storage basins, a plausible design envelope emerges in which antecedent lake levels may stand 0.25–0.50 m higher than present during critical storm sequences. For example, process-based projections for the Laurentian Great Lakes indicate that an $\approx 10\%$ increase in over-lake precipitation and basin runoff would drive a 0.19–0.44 m rise in mean lake stage by the 2040s [64]. Complementary data-driven analyses of a groundwater-fed lake in Germany show that inter-annual stage dynamics are “mainly controlled by climatic variations,” with precipitation acting as the dominant recharge flux [65], and historical hydrographs confirm that record-high Great Lakes levels coincide with multi-year wet periods [64].

Drawing on our rainfall-stage analysis (Sect. 2.2) and published projections of mid-century lake-level rise, we designed Block C to assess the extent by which elevated initial water surfaces amplify flood risk under each design storm. Specifically, we retain the bathymetry configuration and repeat each return-period hyetograph while raising the initial stage. Block C therefore retains the bathymetry configuration and repeats each return-period storm while systematically raising the initial lake level by 0.00, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.25 and 1.50 m. The resulting 35 simulations populate a margin-to-failure curve that expresses minimum freeboard as a function of antecedent stage—an operationally tractable indicator of overtopping risk under potential climate-driven lake-level rise.

3.3.3. Crest-to-gauge freeboard

The water-surface elevation is sampled at Gauge 01, the open-water cell that coincides—within < 2 m—with the pressure-transducer station used for the stage observations (location already shown in Fig. 4). The point lies 24 m lake-ward of the berm face, well inside the quasi-equipotential pool; spatial gradients in the baseline run are < 2 mm,

so the cell furnishes a stable proxy for basin stage.

$$F(t) = z_{\text{crest}} - \eta_{\text{lake}}(t) \quad (5)$$

where z_{crest} is the hydraulic-centre elevation of the sill cell and $\eta_{\text{lake}}(t)$ is the instantaneous stage at Gauge 01. The event statistic

$$F_{\text{min}} = \frac{\min_{t \in N_0} F(t)}{t \in N_0} \quad (6)$$

is extracted for every simulation in Blocks B and C. Because both the crest datum and gauge coordinates remain invariant, F_{min} is directly comparable across lake-representation schemes and antecedent stage increments.

The Australian Technical Flood-Risk Management Guideline 7–3 [66] defines six hazard classes (H1–H6) as joint functions of flow depth h , velocity u and their product $DV=hu$. We have adopted the DV thresholds as a conservative surrogate and merged the two sub-classes that share the range $0.30\text{--}0.60 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (H2/H3). Pixels have therefore been grouped into five display bands: H1 (< 0.30), H2/H3 ($0.30\text{--}0.60$), H4 ($0.60\text{--}1.00$), H5 ($1.00\text{--}4.00$) and H6 ($\geq 4.00 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

3.3.4. Simulation inventory

The full simulation inventory is summarized in Table 3. Block A contains the single calibration run, Block B the ten lake-representation experiments (five return periods \times two DEM treatments), and Block C the thirty-five stage-increment simulations described above. Together these three blocks constitute 46 hydrodynamic realizations, to ensure that every subsequent result can be traced unambiguously to a unique combination of hydraulic configuration, design storm and antecedent lake level.

4. Results

4.1. Calibration performance

Modeled stage follows the measured hydrograph closely—RMSE = 0.061 m and MAE = 0.055 m—and both series exhibit minimal variation beyond these error bounds (Fig. 15). It should be mentioned, however, that stage is not as responsive to rainfall peaks, which be partially explained by the mild slopes and infiltration characteristics that govern the water basin. The simulation reproduces both the absolute envelope (88.28–88.33 m a.s.l.) and the cumulative rise of ≈ 5 cm generated by the 46 mm storm sequence, with only a uniform ~ 2 cm negative bias after 12 July—most plausibly an artefact of daily-averaging of the simulated water stage, rather than a hydrodynamic deficiency. The muted stage response (< 0.10 m rise despite 46 mm rainfall) confirms that the lake acts as an effective storage reservoir that attenuates inflow peaks through its surface area ($\approx 1.2 \text{ km}^2$) and volume capacity. This damping behavior is consistent with hydrologic theory: in small closed lake basins with limited riverine inflow and gently sloping terrain, the water-storage capacity of the lake dampens stage response to precipitation events, attributable to distributed surface-water inputs rather than concentrated channelized discharge [67].

4.2. Lake representation comparison (Block B)

Fig. 16 shows that both models confine the flood wave within the

Table 3

Model-run matrix used in the study.

Block	Configuration(s)	Return period(s)	Stage increment(s) (m)	Runs	Purpose
A Calibration	Bathymetry	Observed storm (10 – 14 Jul 2024)	Measured stage	1	Parameter estimation
B Lake-representation	Bathymery & bare	1, 2, 5, 10, 50 yr	0	10	Effect of DEM treatment on Qp, depth, velocity
C Stage-increment sensitivity	Bathymetry	1, 2, 5, 10, 50 yr	0 \rightarrow 1.50 (0.25 m step)	35	Margin-to-failure curve; freeboard statistics
Total	—	—	—	46	—

basin; no cultural-mound cells are ever wetted. The Bathy run reproduces the surveyed basin, with 6–8 m depths at the center and steep side slopes. In the bare configuration run, maximum depth falls below 1 m, forming a broader yet shoreline-bound layer. The contrasting depth distributions reflect fundamentally different hydraulic initial conditions. The bathymetry configuration initializes 8 m of water depth with realistic storage geometry. In contrast, the bare DEM, which cannot capture subsurface topography from airborne returns, treats the lake as a flat, dry surface. Such misrepresentation forces the model to "fill" an artificial basin during simulation, distorting storage-release dynamics at the outlet.

Flow remains sluggish in both configurations (Fig. 17): 95 % of wet cells register velocities below 0.05 m s^{-1} . The bare model introduces patchy streaks up to $\sim 0.25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ where the artificial flatbed forces water to seek a preferential outlet, but these eddies dissipate before contacting the heritage ridge. Consequently, the DEM treatment has only a second-order effect on kinematic energy and does not threaten the site under the calibrated T_{50} storm.

At the lake outlet, accounting for bathymetry increases simulated peak flows by more than an order of magnitude. The amplification is strongest for frequent (low-return-period) events—rising from $\sim 10 \times$ for the 50-year flood to $\sim 57 \times$ for the 1-year flood—indicating that the use of bare-DEMs underestimates discharge under more common flow conditions (Fig. 18). This occurs even though the land-cover assigned Manning's n values remains the same for both the bare and bathymetry configurations within Block B ($n = 0.025$ for permanent water; Table 2). Instead, the amplification stems from differences in topographic representation and initial conditions. In the bare configuration, the lake is depicted as a flat surface (it reflects photogrammetric acquisition limitations, where signals bounce off the water rather than penetrating it), and leads to artificial ponding of rainfall and upstream inflows on this shallow, dry-initiated plane. Such a representation impounds water inefficiently, delays the outflow and underestimates peak discharges, particularly for frequent events where storage artifacts dominate. By contrast, the bathymetry-integrated DEM incorporates realistic subsurface depths (up to 8 m) with pre-storm wet cells. This configuration accounts for the lake storage capacity, higher hydraulic heads, and therefore more accurate volume propagation when rainfall is added. Critically, infiltration plays no role, as both configurations assign CN = 100 to lake areas (zero losses; Table 2).

The return period amplification ($57 \times$ for T_1 vs. $10 \times$ for T_{50}) indicates that storage errors dominate during low-intensity events, while extreme storms eventually overwhelm both configurations, reducing the relative differences. This finding aligns with the bathymetric uncertainty literature: Garrote et al. [68] demonstrated that omitting river bathymetry in flood models produces flow-depth errors of 0.5–0.75 m when using natural roughness coefficients. These errors propagate nonlinearly through hydraulic simulations, leading to mischaracterization of inundation extent. Our results extend this principle to lacustrine systems, where bathymetric omission systematically underestimates outlet discharge by an order of magnitude, thereby mischaracterizing downstream flood hazards. For heritage risk assessment, this implies that bare-DEM models may falsely indicate safety by underpredicting peak flows that could trigger overtopping at vulnerable structures.

Fig. 15. Comparison of observed and modeled WSE from July 10 to July 14, 2024, following model calibration.

Fig. 16. Simulated water-depth panels at 00:00, 03:00, 06:00 and 09:00 h into the 50-year synthetic hyetograph.

4.3. Stage-increment sensitivity

Across all design storms (Fig. 19), margin-to-failure declines linearly: every 0.25 m rise in lake stage reduces freeboard by ~ 0.40 m. The five curves nearly overlap (spread < 0.04 m), indicating that, with explicit bathymetry, wave setup and seiche cannot distinguish a 1-yr event from a 50-yr one. Even at +1.50 m antecedent raise, over 1.0 m clearance remains, showing the monument’s safety derives from available storage, not rainfall rarity.

Fig. 20 displays peak inundation depth around the heritage mound for the six antecedent-stage increments (+0.25 \rightarrow +1.50 m, T_{50} storm).

With each 25 cm rise the flood tongue climbs uniformly up the berm, yet even at +1.50 m the crest remains dry and the moat that laps the monument never exceeds ≈ 0.35 m. Water is exiting the lake system from the outlet, as displayed in Fig. 4 and the discharge results in Fig. 18. With a near-planar hydrostatic gradient, depths increase uniformly by a constant offset, shifting the colour ramp landward without creating new channels. No localised over-deepenings emerge along the archaeological façade, since water accumulation is entirely pluvial.

Fig. 21 recasts the peak-depth scenes in as DV hazard classes. Across the full Δz sweep every wetted cell falls into H1, the “generally safe” band of the Australian guideline. Higher antecedent stages expand the

Fig. 17. Simulated flow-velocity panels at 00:00, 03:00, 06:00 and 09:00 h into the 50-year synthetic hyetograph.

Fig. 18. Lollipop plot of the bathymetry / bare peak-flow ratio at the lake outlet for return periods of 1, 2, 5, 10, and 50 years, showing how inclusion of bathymetry multiplies predicted peak discharges by roughly 10–57 × compared to a bare-DEM scenario.

H1 (‘safe’) zone upslope, yet no cell in the heritage buffer exceeds H1 even at $\Delta z = 1.50$ m. Thus, the flow regime stays mild; only the area of shallow flooding grows with stage, not the force applied to the monument.

5. Discussion

Results show that explicit bathymetry alters lake-flood dynamics in the RoG model. Using the true basin DEM produces higher peak outflows and deeper inundation than the flat-bed bare DEM. This matches Tilano et al. [69], who found bathymetry matters most in moderate floods and less so in extremes. In our runs, bathymetry peak discharge is $\approx 50 \times$ the bare case for the 1-year storm, shrinking to $\approx 10 \times$ for the 50-year event. A basin funnels rain toward the outlet, while a flat bed spreads it thinly with little gradient. Tilano et al. [69] observe a similar behavior: shallower (sediment-filled) lake beds yield higher water levels and larger flooded extents in moderate flows, but during peak flows the differences

between bathymetric scenarios become “practically negligible”. This points to an important principle – for frequent, sub-extreme events, neglecting submerged terrain can grossly misestimate runoff retention and routing, whereas in rare extremes both accurate and simplified models’ trend toward complete saturation of the basin.

Results reinforce that high-resolution topographic data, including underwater geometry, are not optional luxuries but essential for reliable flood modeling. Prior work has quantified the errors introduced by omitting such data. Cook & Merwade [70] show that omitting channel bathymetry in a LiDAR DEM can bias flood extent by $\sim 15\text{--}20\%$. In our case, the bare DEM (effectively assuming a constant lake stage as the topographic surface) misrepresents a river’s cross-section. The flood-plain response is fundamentally altered – the bare model artificially impounds water in a broad, shallow layer. By contrast, using the bathymetry configuration, the model converts rainfall to runoff more efficiently and yields faster and higher peak flows. The divergence emphasizes what previous hydraulic studies have noted: the geometric capacity of depressions or channels critically controls floodwave propagation. Put simply, if a model ignores where water can go and be stored (e.g. within a lake’s depth), it may misjudge how much water spreads overland.

In the extreme scenarios, both DEMs converged, suggesting a supply-limited regime. When the system is fed by a 50-year downpour, the unnaturally shallow lake (bare DEM) eventually spills and approaches the outflow volumes of the real lake model. Tilano et al. [69] similarly found that bathymetric differences exert a “more noticeable effect for moderate flows than for maximum flows”, with peak-flow water levels virtually identical across different lake bed conditions. In our study, the bathymetry-induced peak flow amplification drops from $\sim 55 \times$ (for a 1-year event) to $\sim 11 \times$ (50-year), so the relative benefit of correct bathymetry is greatest for ordinary flood events. Practically, accurate bathymetry is most critical for moderate floods that recur every decade and strain infrastructure. A model without proper lake geometry might overestimate the buffering for such events, lulling managers into a false sense of security. Conversely, in the face of a catastrophic storm, even a poor topographic representation will predict widespread inundation (if not the exact timing), so the modeling risk is lower. The challenge for engineering practice is that design and planning typically focus on those intermediate return periods – precisely where our results show the choice of DEM can flip a site’s flood outlook, from safe to endangered.

The RoG method collapses the boundary between hydrological and hydraulic modeling, which allows us to simulate the entire chain from

Fig. 19. Minimum crest-to-lake freeboard as a function of antecedent lake-stage increment (Δz) for design storms of 1-, 2-, 5-, 10- and 50-year return period; the inverted axis places zero freeboard at the top.

Fig. 20. Peak water-depth encroachment under the 50-year design storm as antecedent lake level is artificially raised.

Fig. 21. Peak depth-velocity-squared (DV^2) hazard for the 50-year storm under progressive antecedent stage rise.

precipitation to overland flow in one coherent 2D model. This holistic strategy has been advocated in recent years as computing power and data availability have improved. By applying rainfall uniformly across the mesh and letting the shallow-water equations determine runoff paths, we inherently capture micro-topographic effects that traditional lumped runoff models or 1D river models would miss. Our calibration, achieving an RMSE on lake stage (~ 0.06 m) on par with the gauge accuracy, attests to the viability of RoG even in a data-sparse context. Under all simulated scenarios, the relics remain unflooded. Neither the calibrated July 2024 event nor any of the 1–50-year design storms produce water levels high enough to overtop the fortification's crest. In fact, even a hypothetically extreme lake level rise of +1.5 m that far exceeds observed inter-annual fluctuations, leaves roughly one meter of freeboard intact (Fig. 19). Pluvial flooding alone is very unlikely to endanger the cultural asset in its current state. The site's topographic setting (a raised isthmus and earthwork) affords substantial natural protection, which decouples it from all but the most extraordinary flood conditions. It is worth contrasting this with many cultural heritage sites documented in literature that face recurrent flood threats. For example, coastal UNESCO sites in the Mediterranean are already seeing frequent inundation; Reimann et al. [71] mention that 37 of 49 low-lying coastal heritage sites are at risk from a present-day 100-year flood. By comparison, our inland case study appears secure against floods up to the 50-year level. This shifts concern from acute inundation to subtler stresses—moisture cycling, eutrophication, and decay. Practically, stakeholders could shift from costly flood defenses to monitoring long-term lake levels and water quality, which pose greater risks.

It is also instructive to examine why no hazardous flooding occurs in our scenarios. The combination of gentle basin slopes (0.2–0.8 %) and large storage volume in the lake yields a highly attenuating system. Rainfall of even 50-year intensity is mostly absorbed as lake level rise (~ 0.3 – 0.4 m in the worst case) and mild outflow, rather than rapid overland flow. Flow velocities remain very low over the archaeological ridge (≤ 0.05 m s⁻¹, Fig. 17), and depth–velocity products never exceeded the lowest hazard class (H1) even at the inundation fringes. Essentially, the lake functions as a detention basin by temporarily storing inflowing stormwater within its expansive volume and gentle topography. It is gradually releasing it through the narrow outlet at controlled rates, and minimizes overtopping risks at the adjacent heritage site. The finding aligns with the broader understanding that “bathtub” models (simple filling of depressions) can seriously mislead if used in place of physics-based simulation [72]. In reality, the lake did not behave like a static bathtub with instant uniform filling; instead, the dynamic model captures the gradual expansion of a wetting front and the timing of overflow. Sanders et al. [73] emphasize this distinction, noting that simplistic static inundation approaches consistently underperform relative to full hydrodynamic models. Our results exemplify that point: a static approach might assume a uniform lake level rise translates immediately to flood depth against the earthwork, whereas the 2D simulation shows that any overflow is delayed and diminished by the lake's own capacity and outlet flow. This outcome is encouraging for site preservation – it indicates a considerable inherent resilience.

Regional trends suggest mean lake stages may rise by a few cm per decade. To stress-test the system, we imposed incremental lake level rises in Block C simulations. The roughly linear freeboard decline (~ 40 cm lost per +25 cm stage) we found implies that even under a compounded scenario of a 50-year storm following a +0.5 m climatic lake rise, the fortification would still not flood. This margin-to-failure gives confidence that the potential of moderate future precipitation increases alone is unlikely to tip the balance. Only under highly exaggerated conditions (+1.5 m lake rise, beyond credible mid-century predictions) did the moat around the mound reach ~ 0.3 m depth – still below any structural threshold of concern. Such a conservative analysis suggests that the primary climate-related threat to the site is not outright inundation but rather the more gradual effects of moisture regime shifts (e.g. more frequent soil saturation could accelerate rot in wooden structures

just above the water table, even if those structures are never submerged in a flood). In short, our flood hazard model signals “all clear” for overtopping risk in the coming decades; however, it should be integrated with broader vulnerability assessments that include material weathering under increased humidity or human factors like land-use change in the basin.

While the model confirms that surface inundation thresholds are not breached under any tested scenario, the subsurface zone adjacent to the monument becomes increasingly saturated with each stage increment. Drawing on experimental decay studies at Biskupin, such oscillatory conditions at shallow burial depths, especially those hovering near the water table, may enable microbial colonization and trigger rapid deterioration of archaeological oak, even without direct exposure to surface flows. Thus, the absence of overt flooding does not equate to preservation safety. To quantify those risks, a 10-year burial experiment on archaeological oak [18], mass loss and biochemical degradation varied sharply with depth: shallow burial at 25 cm, particularly in mineral soils, corresponds to high-risk preservation zones. At 25 cm depth, waterlogged oak is saturated only 2–3 months each spring, which leaves extended aerobic exposure the rest of the year. The conditions lead to severe degradation: mass loss approaches 76 %, basic wood density decreases by nearly 67 % (leaving only 33.1 % residual density), and maximum water content increases by 328.3 % [18]. Volume loss reaches approximately 27 %, which further translates into a surface layer erosion of around 0.7 mm. Microscopic inspection confirms extensive deterioration of secondary cell wall layers, with hemicelluloses and cellulose largely depleted, leaving thinner cell walls.

In contrast, oak samples buried at an intermediate depth of 50 cm in peat display moderate degradation. These specimens are subject to seasonal water table fluctuations, remaining submerged for roughly half the year. Although peat harbors more microbes than mineral soil, oak at 50 cm depth shows markedly better preservation than in shallow layers. Water content increases by 39.4 %, and porosity rises by 12.6 % [18], but basic density declines by only 19.8 %. The metrics suggest that intermediate burial layers form a transitional preservation regime that is sensitive to both groundwater dynamics and substrate chemistry.

Oak buried at 100 cm, either in waterlogged peat or in water-filled trenches, shows optimal preservation. Conditions like these may mirror the anaerobic environments historically responsible for preserving sites like Biskupin and, potentially, Smuszewo. At this depth, mass loss is limited to just 8–10 % over the decade-long trial, with maximum water content increases ranging from 11.0–16.5 %, and density decreases constrained to 6.4–9.1 %. Volume loss is negligible (~ 2 %), and indicates a stable microenvironment conducive to long-term organic preservation. Redox potential measurements consistently remain below -100 mV, a threshold widely recognized as protective for buried wood.

Chemical analyses confirm degradation varies with burial depth. In severely degraded shallow samples, holocellulose content falls from 356.0 kg/m³ in control samples to just 63.6 kg/m³, a more than five-fold reduction. Cellulose declines similarly—from 210.2 kg/m³ to 36.6 kg/m³—indicating a near-total loss of structural polysaccharides [18]. By comparison, well-preserved samples from 100 cm retain 14–19 % of their original holocellulose and 14–16 % of cellulose. Lignin, while more resilient, still shows a notable decrease, with residual content dropping from ~ 90 % in deep burial conditions to as low as 45.4 % in shallow degraded wood. The holocellulose-to-lignin ratio fell at all depths, with the steepest drop at 25 cm.

Complementary trials using contemporary, non-degraded oak buried at the same site emphasize the fragility of archaeological material. In both wet peat and submerged trench environments, fresh wood exhibits only 3.6–3.8 % mass loss over 10 years. Degradation is largely restricted to hemicellulose components, with minimal shifts in cellulose and lignin. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy confirms the biochemical pathway: attenuation of the 1730 cm⁻¹ absorption band, associated with acetyl and carbonyl groups in xylan, identifies hemicellulose as the primary target of decay. In contrast, archaeological oak degrades 2.5 ×

faster under the same conditions, likely due to loss of protective extractives. It is therefore emphasized that archaeological oak, even when reburied under seemingly favorable conditions, remains highly vulnerable if its biochemical resilience has already been compromised.

Finally, this study illustrates a replicable framework for cultural heritage flood risk assessment that capitalizes on emerging technologies. The use of drone-derived topography allowed us to model the terrain with a high resolution, and allows us to capture the subtle basin morphology that coarser datasets would miss. Trepekli et al. [74] have shown that such ultra-high-resolution elevation models can improve flood predictions as their experiments in urban Ghana reveal that using a 0.3 m-resolution UAV LiDAR DTM reduces flow prediction errors by up to 62.5 % in flat areas compared to a 10 m DEM. Our work adds evidence from a different environment (a natural lake and archaeological mound) that local-scale surveying is well worth the effort for CH sites. Without the drone survey, precise hydraulic modeling would not have been possible; any analysis based on off-the-shelf terrain data (e.g. 5–10 m with water surfaces unpenetrated) would have defaulted to something like our bare DEM case. By representing actual bathymetry, we ensure the model's physics—and its “no hazard” outcome—are credible. The framework also illustrates the importance of multi-scenario sensitivity testing. Rather than a single deterministic statement (“site will not flood for X-year event”), we have mapped a continuum of lake-level scenarios and storm return periods. Besides aligning with UNESCO guidelines for resilient heritage management [6], a similar approach could provide heritage managers a richer understanding: e.g., *even under worst-case lake levels, a 50-year storm leaves ~1 m freeboard*, and conversely, *it would take an unprecedented combination of factors to cause flooding*. Under compound climate stresses, nuanced, site-specific risk appraisals are essential. They allow for informed prioritization – sites that emerge as low risk for floods (like Smuszewo in pluvial terms) can focus on other issues, whereas truly flood-prone sites would warrant immediate adaptation measures.

However, the model implementation in the present study contains three principal limitations that warrant consideration. Event-based calibration, adopted to reduce computational demands, introduces parametric uncertainty through event-dependent parameter optimization [75], leading to divergent parameter sets across calibration events that constrain transferability beyond the calibration domain [76]. Hereby, the RoG configuration assumes spatially uniform precipitation, which constitutes a simplification justified by the basin's modest extent (~23 km²); this assumption would require reconsideration for larger catchments where distributed rainfall representation becomes necessary to capture spatial variability effects on runoff generation mechanisms [77]. Topographic data quality exerts governing influence on flood model accuracy, as systematic errors from DEM acquisition methods propagate through the hydrologic-hydraulic modeling chain, affecting derived terrain parameters and subsequent hydraulic simulations [78].

The divergent risks identified in this study compel decision-makers to prioritize management strategies based on nuanced risk classification, requiring a critical trade-off assessment. Given the site's considerable inherent resilience against pluvial overtopping, the marginal utility of investing in costly structural flood defenses is low. Conversely, the finding that subsurface saturation drives severe material degradation, exemplified by the rapid decay of archaeological oak near the water table (up to 76 % mass loss at 25 cm depth), indicates that the primary threat is hydrological stability, not hydrodynamic force. Therefore, managers must execute a strategic pivot: shifting resources away from traditional flood defenses toward adaptive soil moisture management [79]. This decision-making process inherently involves balancing competing objectives under uncertainty, particularly between the need for model precision, as high-resolution bathymetry and computational intensity guarantee higher accuracy, and the constraints of available budgetary and technical resources [80,81]. The optimal preservation strategy is thus defined not by eliminating surface risk, but by implementing multi-objective frameworks that minimize the

long-term, irreversible material decay caused by moisture regime shifts [82,83].

6. Conclusions

In this work, we aimed to resolve lake-flood dynamics at high spatio-temporal resolution in order to assess the flood risk at one's of Poland's main cultural heritage sites. To this aim, we implemented a two-dimensional RoG methodology in HEC-RAS by combining drone-photogrammetry-derived overland terrain (via a Yuneec H520 RTK drone equipped with a 20-megapixel E90X camera) with a georeferenced, interpolated bathymetric model from the IRŚ plan. This novel integration leveraged ALS for basin-wide topography, drone-derived digital terrain models with 2–3 cm RMS accuracy, and a ventilated DL/N64 sensor for real-time lake-stage monitoring with 0.1 % precision. We applied this workflow to Czeszewo Lake in Smuszewo, Poland, assessing flood hazard across design storms (1–50-year return periods) and systematic lake-level increments (0–1.50 m), informed by continuous high-accuracy measurements (0.1 % precision, <3 mm in practice) from the water level recorder stabilized via a leveled underground benchmark. The RoG framework employed a structured mesh with Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy stability criteria, boundary conditions along basin limits, and land-cover-based hydraulic parameterization (Manning's n : 0.025–0.100; Curve Numbers: 71–100). The resulting margin-to-failure curve provides a concise, operational metric for monitoring potential overtopping at heritage sites.

Despite recent advances in hydraulic modeling, the treatment of lake bathymetry and initial water surface elevation in RoG meshes has remained largely ad hoc, with limited understanding of their effects on overtopping thresholds. Accurate representation of lake bathymetry is the primary determinant of hydraulic fidelity in RoG simulations for lake-fringed floodplains. Introducing the 8 m basin depth increased peak discharges by an order of magnitude and advanced flood arrival times relative to a flat-bed surrogate, demonstrating that simplified terrain misrepresents both flow magnitude and timing for design-level storms due to artificial ponding on flat, dry-initiated surfaces (vs. realistic depths and wet cells enabling accurate volume propagation). Bathymetry omission biased flood extents by 15–20 % and underestimated peaks by up to 55x in moderate events, though differences diminished in 50-year extremes as basins saturated. Velocities stayed mild, with all areas rated safe (H1 class) even at peak stages. Despite this sensitivity, all scenarios—including a 50-year storm imposed on a +1.5 m antecedent stage—maintained at least 1 m of freeboard at the Smuszewo fortification, which confirms that available storage, rather than statistical storm rarity, may govern present overtopping risk. The linear decline of freeboard (~0.40 m per 0.25 m stage rise) provides a tractable metric for operational monitoring. Methodologically, the combination of digital technologies (e.g. drones), high-resolution digital elevation models and advanced RoG hydraulic modeling offers a replicable protocol; omitting submerged geometry leads to systematic underestimation of hazard for moderate-return events, the regime most relevant to routine conservation planning. This resilience decouples the site from acute pluvial threats, redirecting focus to subtler risks like moisture cycling and microbial decay in waterlogged oaks, as observed in long-term studies.

Future heritage risk assessments should therefore treat bathymetric acquisition as a non-negotiable input especially when moderate-frequency flood scenarios are of interest in order to properly evaluate site vulnerability. Overall, our proposed work illustrates the potential of multiscale data and physics-based RoG modeling, laying groundwork for emerging applications like digital twins and cloud-based simulations in heritage flood management.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M.J. Alexopoulos: Conceptualization, Formal analysis,

Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Data curation. **T. Iliopoulou**: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **P. Modé**: Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **D. Istrati**: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **D. Koutsoyiannis**: Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **S. Królewicz**: Data curation, Methodology, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **R. Graf**: Data curation, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **L. Kaczmarek**: Data curation, Methodology, Resources. **W. Rączkowski**: Data curation, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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